

autoFISH: TTL synchronization with Leica Thunder

Short name: autofish_TTL-Leica-Thunder

Version: 2

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Abstract: This protocol uses the trigger module to set up an autoFISH experiment on a Leica THUNDER.

- **Fluidics** exchange is handled by our automated fluidics system, which Python controls.
- **Imaging** is done with the Leica Thunder.
- **With our control software and a triggered acquisition on the microscope, automated** cycles alternating between imaging and fluidics exchange can be performed.

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1 General workflow

- Buffer exchanges are performed with **autoFISH**, imaging with the LEICA Thunder.
- Each fluidic run is accompanied by an **imaging run**. To allow such an acquisition, we treat this as a time course, where each time point corresponds to a fluidics run.
- It requires an **Arduino** to send TTL pulses; information can be found [here](#).
- **TTL ports** have to be specified once (see the section below).

1.1 Getting started

1. **Turn on microscope**
 - a. Turn on camera, power supply, LEDs, and control box
 - b. Start acquisition software (LAS X)
2. **Turn on the fluidics system**
 - a. Turn on all components (switch on the power switch)
 - b. Start Visual Studio code

1.2 Fluidics system

- Instructions for how to use the fluidics system can be found [here](#).
- An important parameter is the **number of fluidic runs**, which will also be used to set the trigger in the microscope control software.

1.2.1 Flow sensor

1. Start the software “USB RS485 Sensor Viewer.”
2. Fill out as shown below. The first field is COM hardware; this will populate the rest of the menu.

1.3 Microscope

1. Set up your experiment as usual (multi-position, multi-color,...)
2. **Change the default shutter behavior** to turn off the LED when waiting for a trigger.
 - a. Open Project settings
 - b. Set shutter control to **After each image**
3. Define a **time course**: each time point corresponds to a fluidic run
 - a. The **time points** (cycles) correspond to the number of fluidic runs **PLUS ONE**. This is to correct for the last trigger signal sent by the Thunder being too short to be recognized. Acquisition of this additional time-point must be canceled after the autoFISH runs are terminated.
 - b. Press on ‘Minimize’ to reduce the time between time points to avoid unnecessary waiting

1.3.1 Multiple regions with autofocus and focus map

1. In the Navigator, go to Stage and disable Optimize Acquisition order of Regions.
2. Go to each region and add a Focus map point (blue cross with F).
3. Once added, click on Focus map.
4. Go through the list of each focus map point; adjust focus as needed and press Set Z.
5. Go to the first position
 - a. Define z-stack as required
 - b. Move to the centre position
 - c. Open Autofocus
 - i. Select Adaptive Focus Control from the drop-down menu.
 - ii. Enable ACF/on.
 - iii. Operation mode: on demand mode.
 - iv. Enable SET AFC position

1.3.2 Set up trigger: start acquisition

1. Go to triggering
2. Select Trigger: TTL_acq_START
3. In the menu, select the following options
 - a. **Trigger linked to acquisition:** enable
 - b. **Channels:** First channel only
 - c. **Timelapse:** Every cycle
 - d. **Stage:** First position only
 - e. **Z pos:** First position only
 - f. **Record trigger signals:** enable

1.3.3 Set up trigger: acquisition finished

1. Go to triggering.
2. Select Trigger: TTL_acq_END

3. In the menu, select the following options (some shown in screenshots):
 - a. **Use in experiment:** enable
 - b. **Number of pulses:** 1
 - c. **Duration (ms):** 1000
 - d. In the lower part, set for **Trigger** to `After acquisition`.
 - e. **Channels:** add the number of channels that you have, e.g., 2
 - f. **Time-lapse:** `every cycle`
 - g. **Stage:** Here, the index of the last field-of-view (FOV) of the last region has to be added, which corresponds to the total number of FOVs that will be imaged.

BUG in software: The field is grayed out; selecting a region gives a default list (2,4,5).

 - Current workaround:
 - In the **task list** (right part of the interface):
 - Right-click on the last region and select `Define trigger`
 - Select `TTL_acq_END`
 - Enable `Trigger after acquisition`
 - Enable the last region
 - In the trigger section
 - Select `start acquisition trigger`, select `at positions`, and select one region. This will add a value,
 - Go to `acquisition finished trigger`. Now, you can select the last region, and the position index will be appropriately updated.
 - Go back to `start acquisition trigger` and revert to first position only.
 - h. **Z pos:** number corresponding to the number of channels, e.g., 9

⚠ CRITICAL: if you don't set this right, triggers might be sent too early or not.

1.4 Launch sequential run

1. **autoFISH**
 - a. Specify acquisition: select TTL sync
 - b. Select the file with settings in the new GUI and press the `Connect to Sync` box.
2. **Leica Thunder**
 - a. Press `Start` – acquisition should not start
 - b. If it does start, you might not have connected to the Arduino.
3. **autoFISH**
 - a. Press `Initiate controller`

- b. Press `Launch acquisition`
4. **Leica Thunder**
 - a. We defined one time-point more than hybridization runs, so once all runs are finished, the acquisition run must be terminated manually by pressing `Stop`.

2 TRIGGER specifications

2.1 Specify TTL ports

This needs to be done only once.

1. Open LASX configurator (other application)
2. Select `Configure (button) > Sequencer Advance > TTL signal`
3. Press the `Add TTL trigger`
 - a. Select trigger port
 - b. Rename to either `TTL_acq_START` or `TTL_acq_END`
 - c. Connect with: *nothing needed to be defined*
 - d. Define as Input/output
 - e. Active: High

3 Version history and archiving

Version	Date	Modified by	Changes
v1	31.10.2024	Mueller F	Initial version.
v2	1.3.2025	Mueller F	Resubmission of autoFISH paper. Improved for clarity.